

THE MAIN STAGES OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE REPUBLIC OF CHINA

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Abstract. *It is stated the main stages of relationship between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of China are. The Republic of Uzbekistan is also interested in establishing mutually beneficial partnership with the PRC in the political, economic, trade, scientific and cultural spheres. Traditional friendly relationship has been established between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of China. It gives opportunity for both countries to conduct mutually beneficial and effective partnership on many issues of mutual interest. On May 11-13, 2017, the state visit of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Republic of China raised Uzbekistan-China relationship to a new step. At the end of the negotiations, Shavkat Mirziyoyev and Xi Jinping signed the Joint Statement between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of China. During his visit to China, Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed 105 mutual documents which cost total 23 billion dollars.*

Keywords: *Republic of Uzbekistan, PRC, strategic partnership, socio-political cooperation, economic relations, diplomatic relations, investment, security.*

ОСНОВНЫЕ ЭТАПЫ ВЗАИМООТНОШЕНИЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН И КИТАЙСКОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ

Аннотация. *Изложены основные этапы взаимоотношений между Республикой Узбекистан и Китайской Республикой. Республика Узбекистан также заинтересована в налаживании взаимовыгодного партнерства с КНР в политической, экономической, торговой, научной и культурной сферах. Между Республикой Узбекистан и Китайской Республикой установились традиционные дружеские отношения. Это дает возможность обеим странам вести взаимовыгодное и эффективное партнерство по многим вопросам, представляющим взаимный интерес. 11-13 мая 2017 года государственный визит Президента Шавката Мирзиёева в Китайскую Республику поднял узбекско-китайские отношения на новую ступень. По итогам переговоров Шавкат Мирзиёев и Си Цзиньпин подписали Совместное заявление между Республикой Узбекистан и Китайской Республикой. В ходе визита в Китай Шавкат Мирзиёев подписал 105 взаимных документов на общую сумму 23 миллиарда долларов.*

Ключевые слова: *Республика Узбекистан, КНР, стратегическое партнерство, общественно-политическое сотрудничество, экономические отношения, дипломатические отношения, инвестиции, безопасность.*

INTRODUCTION

The Republic of China is one of the most powerful countries in the world which plays the most important role in the political, economic, trade, science and cultural spheres Uzbekistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The state independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan was recognized by the Republic of China on December 27, 1991, and diplomatic relationship was established on January 2, 1992. In

Tashkent, in October 1992, the embassy of the PRC began to operate, and in May 1995, the embassy of Independent Uzbekistan in Beijing.

Bilateral relations cover all aspects, and mutual trust relations established between the two countries form the basis of cooperation. In relations between Uzbekistan and China, the commonality of views on terrorism, extremism, separatism, trafficking in drugs and illegal weapons is evident.

The basic principles of long-term and effective Uzbek-Chinese relations are reflected in many documents. Of these “ ” the Treaty on partnership relations of friendship and cooperation (2005.) ”, "Joint declaration on the establishment of strategic partnership (2012.)”, "Treaty of friendship and cooperation (2013.)“, "Joint declaration on the further deepening and development of bilateral strategic cooperation (2013.)”, "Joint declaration on further strengthening Uzbek-Chinese cooperation (2014.) ”, Mutual understanding agreement on strategic cooperation (2016.) And the International Automobile transport Road agreement (2017.) is a proof of our opinion. The contractual and legal basis of Uzbek-Chinese relations has found its reflection in more than 220 documents covering various fronts.

It should be noted that the basis of the rapid development of cooperation relations between the two countries based on mutual interest, equality, and openness lies primarily in the similarity, closeness and harmony of goals and objectives in their development principles and foreign policy strategy.

RESULTS

Mutual visits and meetings of the leaders of the two countries have become a tradition. For example, I. Karimov, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, visited China in 1992, 1994, 1999, 2005, 2011, 2012, and President Sh. Mirziyoyev in 2017. Also, the Presidents of Uzbekistan participated in meetings of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization and other major international events. Presidents of the Republic of China, Jiang Zemin (1996), Hu Jintao (2004, 2010), Xi Jinping (2013, 2016 (during the SCO Tashkent Summit) paid an official visit to Uzbekistan.

On June 20, 2016, the President of the Republic of China, Xi Jinping, spoke about the relations with Uzbekistan and noted that "China and Uzbekistan are equal and mutually beneficial partners who share common interests and destiny, joy and concern." According to him, "2,000 years ago, the Great Silk Road served the noble purposes of establishing friendship, mutual cooperation and mutual enrichment between our nations. Zhang Qian, ambassador of the Xihan Dynasty of China, Xuanzang, the ambassador of the Tang Dynasty, and Chenchen, the ambassador of the Ming Dynasty, came to Uzbekistan with a specific mission or passed through its territory at different times.

Uzbekistan considers the strengthening of strategic cooperation with the Republic of China, the expansion of broad trade-economic, investment and financial cooperation as a priority direction of bilateral relations based on the principles of mutual interest and equality. According to the Bilateral Trade and Economic Agreement (1992), the procedure for creating the greatest convenience in trade and economic relations between the two countries has been established. Currently, China ranks second (after Russia) among Uzbekistan's trade partners.

DISCUSSION

In the process of carrying out economic reforms in the society, it is necessary to note the following commonalities typical for the PRC and Uzbekistan: they have experienced a socialist

economic system, the society has been influenced by the dominant ideology, the abundance of land for agriculture (water shortage), developed industrial enterprises, scientific potential, cheap labor and consists of territorial proximity.

The fact that more than 786 enterprises established with the participation of Chinese capital (95 of them are established on the basis of 100% Chinese investment) are operating in Uzbekistan shows the growing interest of PRC businessmen towards Uzbekistan. Also, representative offices of 73 leading Chinese firms and companies are operating in Tashkent in order to closely study the markets of Uzbekistan.

During his official visit to the Republic of China in May 2017, the President signed contracts worth 22 billion US dollars. Some of these multi-billion dollar projects have been implemented, and the rest are expected to be implemented.

CONCLUSIONS

Bilateral investment partnership relations between the governments of Uzbekistan and the Republic of China are developing in accordance with the program of cooperation in the fields of raw materials and high technologies (2010). Joint projects are being successfully implemented in the oil and gas and telecommunication sectors, transport, textile, chemical industry and other sectors. Chinese business entities participated in the construction of many new industrial giants in Uzbekistan, including the Dehqonabad potassium fertilizers and Kungirotd soda plants. With the support of PRC entrepreneurs, the production of electrical engineering products, mobile phones, and construction equipment was launched in Uzbekistan. "Huawei" company implemented 20 projects for the development of telecommunication networks in Tashkent and other regions. The sale of modems, smartphones and other equipment produced in cooperation with ZTE Corporation in local and foreign markets is very effective.

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